

ПРЕОДОЛЕНИЕ КУЛЬТУРНО-СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИХ ПРОБЛЕМ В ПИСЬМЕННОМ ОБЩЕНИИ В РАМКАХ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ «АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК ДЛЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕЛЕЙ»

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OVERCOMING CULTURALLY-SPECIFIC CHALLENGES IN WRITTEN COMMUNICATION IN EAP

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Аннотация

Письменное общение сегодня является одним из основных способов взаимодействия. Академическое письмо является одним из видов письменной коммуникации. В данной статье будут описаны культурно-специфические барьеры, с которыми сталкиваются студенты неязыковых факультетов в процессе обучения. В ходе анализа применялась количественная методология, которая помогла собрать необходимые данные и рассчитать фактические трудности в сфере академического письма. На основе полученных результатов был разработан специальный комплекс упражнений, который поможет будущим слушателям курса «Английский для специальных целей» усовершенствовать свои языковые навыки и преодолеть наиболее распространенные ошибки.

Abstract

Written communication is one of the main ways of interaction today. Academic writing is one of the types of written communication. This article will describe the culturally specific barriers that students of non-linguistic faculties face during the learning process. During the analysis, a quantitative methodology was applied, which helped to collect the necessary data and calculate the actual difficulties in the field of academic writing. Based on the results obtained, a special set of exercises was developed that will help future students of the English for Specific Purposes course to improve their language skills and overcome the most common mistakes.

Ключевые слова: культурно-специфические вопросы, письменное общение, английский язык для специальных целей, культура, язык, общение.

Keywords: cultural-specific issues, written communication, English for Specific Purposes, culture, language, communication.

Introduction

Communication is a vital aspect of human being. Both: verbal and non-verbal interaction play a significant role in modern world. English is a world-wide language which helps various nationalities and cultures interact with each other. Sometimes written communication can be more difficult than oral. One of the types of written communication is academic writing which is aimed at reading, understanding, and writing scientific texts in a short, concise, and well-structured manner. Moreover, it is significant to mention that there are a lot of culturally-specific features that should be taken into consideration in terms of this type of writing in order to prevent students from certain challenges. There is a course which is called English for Academic Purpose that relates to the usage of English in academic context. Considering certain aspects of written communication in terms of English for Academic Purpose it is difficult to interact easily, there is a diversity of barriers and pitfalls that occur between native speakers and second language speakers. This course can help to avoid such gaps of miscomprehension and even to improve English skills and writing, in particular, to be aware of cultural characteristics and to strengthen communication competencies. In this article culturally-specific challenges

emerging in written communication in EAP will be revealed and some examples from a special set of exercises aimed at improving written skills of students from non-linguistic faculties will be presented.

Methodology that was used in terms of this research relates to the quantitative method. The experiment included two groups of students from non-linguistic faculties such as Faculty of Communications, Media and Design; Faculty of Economic Sciences; Faculty of Computer Technology; Faculty of Social Sciences; Faculty of Biology and Biotechnology; Faculty of Electronics and Mathematics and Faculty of Geography and Geoinformation Technologies.

The notion of English for Academic Purpose. Culturally-specific features of writing in terms of English for Academic Purpose

EAP is decoded as English for Academic Purposes. This type of English important for students of linguistic and non-linguistic faculties, for those people who are in scientific field, working in international corporations and government institutions, for those who want to study abroad. Within English for Academic Purpose course, a person learns language in an academic context. Academic writing also demonstrates knowledge of a person about the usage of foreign language. It is vitally important to follow the rules and

conventions of academic writing, this skill represents the literacy and competence. EAP is included in the sphere of ESP- English for Specific Purpose. And one of the branches of the field of ESP is English for Academic Purpose. there are two specific branches which can be pointed out:

- The first one is called English for General Academic Purpose. In such a course people study writing, reading, listening skills on a general scale, without any further specialization in work or study spheres.

- The second branch is English for Specific Academic Purposes. In this case the accent on specific and particular aspects is made. This type of English for Academic Purpose shows that there are a lot of differences among writing, reading and listening aspects.

Distinguishing features of academic writing of Anglo-American and Continental styles

<i>Anglo-American standards</i>	<i>Continental standards (Slavic and Hungarian languages)</i>
Problematic approach	Broad scope of the problem
The use of the adverbs "why" or "how" at the beginning of a research question	The use of the pronoun "what" or "who" at the beginning of a research question
Absence of ambiguities	Theoretical complexity
Clarity and conciseness of the structure and presentation of material, impersonal style and reasoning	The absence of a clearly expressed problem in a research question and usage of many theoretical works and abundance of metaphors which are used in literary texts
Linear structure (straight to the point)	Chaotic structure, extra information which is not related to the topic can be found

Considering all the written aspect's standards of international academic community the most common issues that Russian students have can be pointed out:

1. Usage of words which are similar in sound or spelling but are different in meaning, creation of new words
2. Implementing of colloquial words and phrases demonstrating non-academic style
3. Wrong usage of collocations
4. Lack of scientific definitions and constant repetition of the words
5. Wrong usage of articles
6. Inconsistency in person or number of subject and predicate

To receive the information about culturally-specific challenges that Russian students face in academic writing an experiment was carried out. Based on the results which were received a special set of exercises is developed in order to improve written skills of students and minimize possible challenges that can impede successful writing.

Experimental research and creation of a set of exercises for students of non-linguistic faculties to improve writing skills in terms of English for Academic Purpose course

The research was carried out among students of the first year who are enrolled on the course of English for Academic Purpose. It consists of two parts. The first stage of the research is an entry investigation that helps to identify culturally-specific challenges which are encountered by students. I analyzed several works of students, which they made at the beginning of the academic year, The second stage of the research is an experiment. The aim of the experiment is to provide results related to the written aspect after a certain period of time. During this period students were divided into

One of the most significant aspects which the course of EAP includes is writing part. Within such type of written communication the following components should be considered: grammar, phonetics, vocabulary and syntax. These aspects are essential parts of effective and successful writing. Within Anglo-Saxon conventions of academic writing, representatives of this culture use a "linear" model of writing. This type is characterized by a clear identification of the main theme, which is supported in the text from the beginning to the very end without any digressions from the main topic. On the contrary, Russian style differs from English. Russian texts are filled with extra information which is not related to main thesis of the work.

two groups. The first group did exercises only from their student's book "Oxford EAP" by Edward de Chazal & Sam McCarter and the second group did some extra exercises besides the exercises from their basic student's book. Further I will provide an article with some certain examples.

Twenty five girls and thirteen boys took part in the experiment and total number of students is thirty eight. All the students were from non-linguistic faculties which are listed above.

The first part of the research includes the investigation of several works of the students of the English for Academic Purpose course in order to establish the issues that they have. Such works as abstracts, summaries, essays were analyzed. These works were done by students at the beginning of the academic year (November- December).

I will present some of the common mistakes below:

1. "*Covid-19 was the problem that affected on educational system all over the world*" (**collocation**)
2. "*UK government discussed increasing the school day. United Nation Education Working Group offers this as a solution to the problem.*" (**Missing the definite article before proper nouns**)
3. "*That's why the government's idea can be valuable for studying in theory but not in practice.*" (**Implementing of colloquial words and phrases which are inappropriate for academic style**)
4. "*But is it reasonable to make a longer working day for teachers? It was found that teachers in England work longer than in other countries and an increasing of number of classes would make teachers dissatisfied.*" (**The inability to use the lexical means of the language and substitute a word with a synonym can demonstrate lack of vocabulary of a student**)

5. "Since the beginning of pandemic teachers has had to work in the state of uncertainty because the format of education has changed dramatically a lot of times, so they had to adopt every time." (Writing a plural noun, for example, and use a verb in a singular form afterwards- common mistake among Russian students)

I presented some examples which clearly demonstrate some obstacles faced by students in terms of writing communication.

The second part of my experiment was connected with creating of a set of exercises aimed at helping the students to improve their language skills in writing sphere. Some of the exercises from this set are presented below:

Exercise №1 Insert a definite article where it is necessary:

1. Our journey started in ___ early morning. Answer- article is needed.

2. ___ UK government is divided in two principal parts: ___ House of Commons and ___ HM Government. Answer: The UK government, the House of Commons, HM Government.

Exercise №2: Rewrite sentences using synonyms to the marked words:

1. There are a lot of companies nowadays and each **company** has its own corporate culture. Answer: organization, firm, etc.

Political system is very complicated hierarchical structure. This **structure** has various divisions and channels. Answer: framework, organization, etc.

Exercise №3: Use singular or plural form of verb to complete the following sentences.

1. Both of them ___ in the highest tower of this business center (work). Answer: work/ are working.

2. Neither shops nor restaurants ___ open during siesta time in Spain (be). Answer: are.

Exercise №4: There is a metaphor in each sentence. Find it and out, explain why this stylistic device should be omitted in academic style?

1. The sun was shining bright, she was standing on the mountain and her blue eyes were diamonds that sparkled in the sunlight. Answer: her blue eyes were diamonds.

2. It is a well-known fact that laughter is the best medicine which helps to get rid of negativity and prolongs life. Answer: laughter is the best medicine.

There are diagrams which show the results of students on different stages. The statistics which will be presented in Diagram-1 below describes the overall quantity of mistakes done by the students of both groups before the experimental research.

Diagram-1

Diagram-2 demonstrates the results of the first group after 5 months of standard studying and diagram-3 depicts the statistics of the second group after 5 months of carrying out the additional tasks.

Diagram-2

Diagram-3

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that Academic writing includes various elements which should be taken into consideration. It is important to remember that Anglo-Saxon writing rules are generally accepted standards for academic writing. Despite the fact that various cultures have different perceptions of written communication and some special characteristics, students of EAP course have to rely on general conventions. Still there are research works connected with the issue of culturally-specific challenges, there is a gap that needed to be investigated more thoroughly and deeper. A larger number of experimental studies will allow to expand sampling and find out more challenges which Russian students face. The aim of the current research paper was achieved and additional materials for the EAP course

were elaborated. This work is a contribution to the actual investigations related with this scope. Academic writing is a topical theme nowadays and avoiding of culturally-specific barriers is a key to efficient and competent expression of your thoughts and ideas.

References

1. Charles M., Pecorari. D. (2016). *Introducing English for Academic Purposes*. Routledge.
2. Hall, E. T. (1976). *Beyond culture*. 1st Edition. NY: Doubleday, Anchor Books.
3. Hyland, K. (2006). *English for academic purposes: An advanced resource book*. Abingdon, United Kingdom: Routledge.

4. Hyland, K., & Hamp-Lyons, L. (2002). EAP: Issues and directions. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*.
5. Kaplan, R.B. (1966). Cultural Thought Patterns in Inter- Cultural Communication. *Language Learning. A Journal of Research in Language Studies*.
6. Mallia, J. (2017). Strategies for Developing English Academic Writing Skills. *Arab World English Journal*
7. Plonski, J. M. (2019). Intercultural Experience and Learning Among EAP International Students. *Electronic Thesis and Dissertation Repository*. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/etd/6066>
8. Ter-Minasova S.G. (2008). *Voyna i Mir Yazykov i Kultur*. Publishing House "Slovo".
9. Torghabeh, R.A., Yazdanmehr, E. (2016). Developing intercultural awareness in English for specific purposes and translation curriculum, pp. 2-7. *Review of Applied Linguistic Research*. Shanid Bahonar University of Kerman
10. Xiuyan, XU. (2012). *Cultural Factors in EAP Teaching -- Influences of Thought Pattern on English Academic Writing*. C.S. Canada Publishing.